

DETERMINANTS OF DIETARY DIVERSITY: EVIDENCE FROM FAISALABAD, PUNJAB

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Abstract

The Household Dietary Diversity Pattern (HDDP) demonstrates the households' economic ability to access variety of foods during a given period of time. Different food groups are defined as household that consumes during a specified period. HDDP as indicator of food security can be influenced by a variety of socio-economic factors such as age, size, family type, education, income of household and gender. This study aimed to investigate the factors affecting household dietary diversity patterns among households in the district of Faisalabad, Punjab. To measure HDDP score twelve food groups (ranging from 0-11) were selected. The cross-sectional survey was used to select a suitable number of respondents. A questionnaire was developed according to the rules of the Food Agriculture Organization to seek data from the respondents. Dietary diversity has been classified into three classes: low, medium, and high, on the basis of consumption of different food groups used in the daily diet. Hence it is a qualitative measure of food consumption so logistics regression was employed. The result showed that gender, type of house, household size, age, family income and sources of income are the most important significant factors with dietary diversity score. On the other hand only family type had the insignificant relation with dietary diversity score. More income, higher education and female headed house had more diet diversity. The study suggested that proper awareness should be created about how to maintain balance of diet and balance of population.

INTRODUCTION

Food security is defined as ensuring all individuals have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritional food to meet their nutritional requirements for an active and healthy lifestyle at all time (Vaitla *et al.*, 2017). It plays an essential role in eliminating hunger in the world and

providing safe nutritional requirements. The household dietary diversity pattern (HDDP) is a population-level indicator to measure food security. It can be defined as the total sum of different food groups consumed by a household over a given period of time. When combined with

other food security indicators, HDDP helps households access to various food groups. Dietary diversity is a useful tool for measuring food security and attaining the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) ending hunger and food insecurity (Mazenda and Mushayanyama, 2022).

The Household Dietary Diversity Pattern (HDDP) relies on four crucial components: availability, stability, accessibility, and utilization. These components ensure that food is consistently available, accessible, and nutritious for all household members. Food availability means food is readily available at home for everyone. Food accessibility: Households can afford to purchase food as needed. Food stability means food is consistent and reliable. Food utilization means that food provides essential nutrients. The reserhc studies has shown that higher HDDP scores are linked to improved socioeconomic status and household food security (Hoddinot and Yohannes, 2002; Hatloy *et al.*, 2000).

Dietary diversity can be measured at the individual level as well as at the household level. Individually, it reflects the adequacy of micronutrients and macronutrients. At the household level dietary diversity indicates economic access of the household towards food and reveals consumption patterns across various food groups. (Fitawek and Hendriks, 2021). Dietary diversity is influenced by the socioeconomic factors such as education, gender, income and household size. Low-income urban households often experience food insecurity, resulting in inadequate intake of essential nutrients. Cultural norms and personal preferences, and resource constraints, which vary with tradition and individual differences (Boulom *et al.*, 2020). Key determinants of dietary diversity include population and wealth, with additional influences from income sources, technological innovation, and climate change (Codjoe *et al.*, 2016).

There are plenty of factors that affect the dietary diversity pattern, such as level of education, low income levels, lack of awareness of consumption patterns, age of household head, distance from the market and price of the food items (Jebessa *et al.*, 2019; Muhammad and Sidique, 2019; Egbetokun *et al.*, 2020; Boz and Shahbaz, 2021; Cordero-Ahiman *et al.*, 2021). Poor health conditions among women, less access to nutrient-dense foods are a significant factor in food insecurity and dietary diversity patterns (Shapu *et al.*, 2020; Bose *et al.*, 2021; Forsido *et al.* 2021).

Therefore, the purpose of the present study is to measure the household dietary diversity score and factors affecting on household dietary diversity pattern. Multiple factors such as age of the household, household head education and household income, size of the family, health expenses, cost of food and different food groups' consumption in the daily diet has been examined.

Materials Methods

Sampling And Data Collection

The study was conducted in the district of Faisalabad Punjab, by using primary data from 120 respondents. A well-structured questionnaire has been developed under the guidelines of FAO (2013). Dietary diversity was estimated by organizing information on household food consumption from a set different food items for 24 hours preceding the survey. All the food items were clustered into twelve food groups: Pulses/grains; Fish/seafood; Fruits; Vegetables; Meat; white root tuber; Dairy products; legumes; sugar; oils and fats and miscellaneous (Table 2.1). Socio-demographic information about the respondents such as age, marital status, education level, number of family members and average household monthly income was collected.

Table 2.1: 12 Food groups for Household Dietary diversity Score (HDDS)

Serial No	Food groups	Examples
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0	Cereals	Corn/maize, rice, wheat, sorghum, millet or any other grains or foods made from these (e.g. bread, noodles, porridge or other grain products) + insert local foods e.g. porridge
1	White tubers	white potatoes, or other foods made from roots
2	Vegetables	Dark green leafy vegetables + locally available vitamin A rich leaves such as spinach, other vegetables (e.g. tomato, onion) + other locally available vegetables
3	Fruits	ripe mango, apricot (fresh or dried), ripe papaya, dried peach, and 100% fruit juice made from these + other locally available vitamin A rich fruits, other fruits, including wild fruits and 100% fruit juice made from these
4	Eggs	eggs from chicken, duck, any other egg
5	Meat	beef, lamb, goat, rabbit, chicken, duck,
6	Fish	fresh or dried fish or shellfish
7	Milk	milk, cheese, yogurt or other milk products
8	Oils	oil, fats or butter added to food or used for cooking
9	Legumes	dried beans, dried peas, lentils, nuts, seeds or foods made from these (e.g. peanut butter)
10	Sweets	sugar, honey, sweetened soda or sweetened juice drinks, sugary foods such as chocolates, candies, cookies and cakes
11	Miscellaneous	Spices (black pepper, salt), condiments (soy sauce, hot sauce), coffee, tea.

Household Dietary Diversity Score (HDDS)

These food group score, a measure of dietary diversity, is counted by adding up the value of the items reflecting the twelve food groups. For each household, the diet diversity can take any value from zero and one. A household would get the value zero if it does not consume any one of the items and it would get the value of one if it consumed items from all food groups. Then sum all the food groups to calculate the household dietary diversity score.

The FAO (2013) identifies three tiers of dietary diversity score. The household dietary diversity score is categorized into three primary levels based on the consumption of several food groups; low, medium and high. A household that consumes (0-3) food groups in last 24 hours has a low dietary diversity score. A household that consumes (4-5) food groups in the last 24 hours has a medium dietary diversity score. If a household consumes (6-11) food groups in last 24 hours it has high dietary diversity score (Table 2.2).

Table 2.2: HDDS Classification (source: FAO 2013)

HDDS	Classification
0-3	Low range between (0-3)
4-5	Medium range between (4 to 5)
6-11	High range between (6 to11)

Ordinal Logistic Regression Model

Ordinal regression is a statistical technique that is used to predict behavior of ordinal level dependent variables with a set of independent variables. The dependent variable is the order

response category variable and the independent variable may be categorical or continuous. This study used the ordered logistic regression method for data analysis because the nature of this data is most suitable to use the ordered logistic regression

method. (Arene and Anyaeji, 2010; Kant *et al.*, 1993). The household dietary diversity pattern was regressed on independent variables to check the impact of those variables on household dietary diversity score. These include gender, age, education, family income, household size and family type.

The relationship between dependent and independent variable is given below

In present study the model was used

$$Y_i = \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \beta_3 X_{i3} + \beta_4 X_{i4} + \beta_5 X_{i5} + \beta_6 X_{i6} + \beta_7 X_{i7} + \mu \quad (3)$$

Y_i =dependent variable (HDDS = household dietary diversity score)

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7$ are the parameters in model to be estimated.

While i observation 1..... k

μ = error term

Are the independent variables. $X_1 X_2 X_3 X_4 X_5 X_6$

X_7

X_1 - Gender

X_2 = Family type

X_3 - Type of house

X_4 = Household size

X_5 - Age of household head

X_6 -Education of household head

X_7 -Family income

Y = Household Dietary Diversity Pattern (HDDP)

Results and Discussions

HDDS in order Category

The dietary diversity is divided into three categories low (1-3), medium (4-5) and highly (6-12) diversified (Nithya, 2018). The research collected data from the urban areas of Faisalabad district, resulting in a high level of household diversification (Table 3.1). 7.5 percent of the respondents exhibited a lower quality diet. While 17.5 percent respondents belongs to medium range of the dietary diversity. Most of the respondents have highly dietary diversity, 75 percent of the respondents from the urban areas consumed almost all the food groups in their daily diet.

In the urban areas people were more conscious about their dietary pattern and food consumption pattern. They consume healthy and nutritious food in their daily diet. Educated households were more conscious towards the dietary diversity due to awareness. The respondents that had more income they were able to consume almost all the food groups in their daily diet. They showed good dietary diversity pattern and they were more food

Table 3.1: Frequency distribution of HDDS for the Households

Y order Category	Frequency	Percent
Low= (0-3)	9	7.5
Medium=(4-5)	21	17.5
High=(6-12)	90	75
Total	120	100

Empirical Analysis

Ordinal Logistic Regression

In this study dependent variable was household dietary diversity pattern. The dependent variable divided into three categories low, medium and high. Many factors were responsible for household dietary diversity pattern (HDDP) such as household size, family type, income, education and gender. The results of ordered logistic regression model for the household characteristics

and dietary diversity pattern shown in Table 3.2. The Chi-square test value is 180.21 and the P-value is less than 0.001 highly significant at the 5 percent level of significance.

This indicates that this model statistically significant which means that the final model is fit. The explanatory variables gender of household head, type of house, household size, education of the household head and family income were found significant while the family type and age of

the household head was found insignificant. Family type, age of the household head and household size were negatively affecting the household dietary diversity. While the family

income positively affects the household dietary diversity.

Table 3.2: Results of ordered logistic Regression

Variables	Coefficient	Std Err	P-value
Gender of household head	1.065	0.087	0.000
Family type	-0.071	0.050	0.937
Type of house	0.766	0.002	0.000
Household size	-2.225	0.029	0.000
Age of the household head	-0.899	0.445	0.043
Education of the household head	1.341	0.064	0.000
Family income	0.554	0.048	0.000
Pseudo R ²		0.786	
P-Value		0.000	

LR chi 2 (7) =180.21

Odd Ratio in ordered Logistic Regression

The odd ratio is the important measure of ordered logistic regression model because it is very useful for the discussion of the result (Field, 2005) explained that odd ratios are measured by dividing probability of an incident happening to the probability of an incident happening to the probability of incidence non-happening. If the value of an independent variable is greater than 1 than the odd of the result positively related to the categorical dependent and if the value of independent variable is less than 1 the odd the result is negatively related to a categorical dependent variable. The mathematical form odd ratio is as follow:

$$\text{Odds} = P_i / 1 - P_i$$

P_i is the probability of event occurrence and 1- P_i is the probability of the events non-occurrence

Gender of the household head has a positive coefficient and significant at the 5 percent. One unit increase in the gender of the household will bring a 0.33 increase in the log-odds of being at a higher category level of Y order, given that all other variables in the model are held constant. Family type has a negative coefficient and insignificant at a level of 5 percent. One unit increase in the family type will bring a 2.6 unit decrease in ordered log-odds of being at higher category level of Y order, given that all of the other variables in the model

are held constant. Type of house has a positive coefficient and significant at the 5 percent. One unit increase in the type of house will bring a .41 unit increase in the ordered log-odds of being in the higher category level of Y order, given that all other variables in the model are held constant. The household size has a negative coefficient and significant at a level of 5 percent. One unit increase in size of household will bring a 1.67 unit decrease in ordered log-odds of being in the higher category (High dietary diversity).

Age of the household head has a negative coefficient and insignificant at a level of 5 percent. One unit increase in age of household head, would expect a 0.93 decrease in ordered log-odds of being in a higher category, given that all of the other variables in the model are held constant. The education of the household head has a positive coefficient in our sample size. One unit increase in education of household head would expect a 5.79 increase in the log-odds of being at a higher category level of Y order, given that all of the other variables in the model are held constant. Family income has a positive coefficient and significant at a level of 5 percent. One unit increase in the family income, would expect .99 increase in ordered log- odds of being at a higher category level of Y order, given that all other variables in the model are held constant.

The value of R^2 is 0.78 that indicates 78 percent variation in the dependent variable (HDDP) is explained by independent variables such as family type, household size, education, gender and income of the household. Family type, age of the household head and household size were

negatively affect the household dietary diversity. While the family income, education of the household head, gender positively affect the household dietary diversity

Table 3.3: Estimated Measure of Odd Ratio in Ordered Logistic Regression

Variables	Odd Ratio	St. Errors	Z-value	P-value
Gender of household head	.3367	.0246584	-5.53	0.000
Family type	2.612	.0792014	-4.63	0.937
Type of house	.4172	.0609539	-6.03	0.000
Household size	1.6792	.3101695	4.20	0.000
Age of the household head	0.932	.118722	5.30	0.043
Education of the household head	5.7945	4.403741	2.31	0.000
Family income	.9964	.34302	-0.02	0.000
Cut point	.3470	.7263		

Food Security and Dietary Behaviors of Respondents

The survey results indicated diverse degrees of food insecurity and understanding concerning nutrition and health among participants (Table 3.4). Approximately 10 percent of households strongly concurred, and 27.5 percent agreed that they omitted meals due to inadequate financial resources for food, signifying that economic limitations lead to meal reduction for certain families. Likewise, 40.8 percent strongly concurred, and 47.5 percent concurred that they or other household members consumed less than necessary, indicating widespread dietary inadequacy. Time constraints emerged as a significant issue affecting eating patterns, with 23.3 percent strongly agreeing that meals were skipped due to lack of time. Regarding income disparities, 35 percent strongly agreed that higher income enhances access to healthy meals, emphasizing socioeconomic inequalities in dietary quality.

A majority of respondents acknowledged that awareness about diet diversity is essential, suggesting that recognition of nutritional knowledge can be a determinant of healthy eating practices. Similarly, 17.5 percent strongly agreed, and 33.3 percent agreed that a healthy diet affects mental condition, while 47.5 percent strongly agree that it also influences restful sleep. Furthermore, 47.5 percent agreed that maintaining a balanced weight is also linked to a healthy diet. Interestingly, the highest level of agreement, which 60 percent strongly agree, has shown that significant link between nutrition and emotional well-being. Overall, the results suggested that many respondents face economic and temporal challenges affecting their dietary patterns, there is widespread understanding of the importance of diet diversity and its importance on physical and mental health.

Table 3.4: Distribution of the respondents towards different statements

Questions	Strongly agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly disagree (%)

Do you think that you and other household member skip meal because there was not enough money to buy food?	10	27.5	37.5	23	2
Do you or other household member ever eat less than you or they would have needed to eat?	40.8	47.5	11.7	5	6.7
Do you or any other member skip meal not have enough time for eating?	23.3	38.3	25.8	6	6.5
People with more income has more access towards a healthy meal?	35	25.8	20.8	13.3	3.5
Do you think that awareness about diet diversity is necessary?	43.3	26.7	17.5	5	7.5
Do you think that healthy diet have impact on mental condition?	17.5	33.3	30.8	17.5	0.8
Does restful sleep is effected by healthy diet?	47.5	32.5	15.8	3.3	0.8
Does balanced weight is related to healthy diet?	45.5	24	19.2	3	8.3
Do you think that mood fluctuated according to diet?	60	18.3	13.3	6.7	1.66

Conclusion

The research on household dietary diversity in urban Faisalabad reveals the critical importance of dietary diversity related to various socioeconomic factors such as gender of household head, type of house, household size, education of the household head and family income, family type, age of the household head, and household size. It emphasizes that access to nutritious food is essential for food security, which is achieved when households can meet their nutritional needs in accordance with food preferences. The study utilized a dietary diversity score and evaluated factors such as income, household size, education levels, and the age of the household head.

Key findings indicate that higher-income households tend to have better dietary variety and nutritional intake. Educated respondents are more conscious of their dietary choices. Conversely, respondents with large families and those lacking property ownership face greater food insecurity. The study employed statistical tools like ordinal logistic regression to analyze the impact of these variables on dietary diversity. The results indicated that gender, type of house, household size, age, family income, and sources of income are the most important factors with dietary diversity score. On the other hand, only the family type had an insignificant relation with the dietary diversity

score. More income, higher education, and a female-headed household had more diet diversity. The study suggested that proper awareness should be created about how to maintain a balance of diet and balance of population. The research also suggested improvements in food security through frameworks like sustainable livelihood and calls for focused policy recommendations to address the issues of food availability and accessibility. It highlights the need for further examination of income-related factors affecting dietary patterns and proposes that household food intake should be recognized as a qualitative measure influenced by socioeconomic factors.

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